

HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS IN INDIA

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In India, the last quarter of the 20th century has been witness to a growing recognition of the place and relevance of human rights. It is axiomatic that this interest in human rights is rooted in the denial of life and liberty that was a pervasive aspect of the Emergency (1975-77). The mass arrests of the leaders of the opposition, and the targeted apprehension of those who could present a challenge to an authoritarian state, are the dominant images that have survived. The involuntary disappearance of Rajan in Kerala is more than a symbol of the excesses of unbridled power. Forced evictions carried out in Delhi in what is known as 'Turkman Gate' conjures up visions of large scale razing of dwellings of those without economic clout, and of their displacement into what were the outlying areas of the city. The catastrophic programme of mass sterilisation is an indelible part of emergency memory.

The civil liberties movement was a product of the emergency. Arbitrary detention, custodial violence, prisons and the use of the judicial process were on the agenda of the civil liberties movement.

The situation of **human rights in India** is a complex one, as a result of the country's large size and tremendous diversity, its status as a developing country and a sovereign, secular, democratic republic, and its history as a former colonial territory. The Constitution of India provides for Fundamental rights, which include freedom of religion. Clauses also provide for Freedom of Speech, as well as separation of executive and judiciary and freedom of movement within the country and abroad.

According to the United States Library of Congress, although human rights problems do exist in India, the country is generally not regarded as a human rights concern, unlike other countries in South Asia. Based on these considerations, the 2010 report of Freedom in the World by

Freedom House gave India a political rights rating of 2, and a civil liberties rating of 3, earning it the highest possible rating of *free*.

In its report on human rights in India during 2010, Human Rights Watch stated India had "significant human rights problems". They identified lack of accountability for security forces and impunity for abusive police including "police brutality, extrajudicial killings, and torture" as major problems. An independent United Nations expert in 2011 expressed concern that she found human rights workers and their families who "have been killed, tortured, ill-treated, disappeared, threatened, arbitrarily arrested and detained, falsely charged and under surveillance because of their legitimate work in upholding human rights and fundamental freedoms."

Several international agencies and the UN have reported human rights violations in Indian-administered Kashmir. In a recent press release the OHCHR spokesman stated "The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights is concerned about the recent violent protests in Indian-administered Kashmir that have reportedly led to civilian casualties as well as restrictions to the right to freedom of assembly and expression."

A 1996 Human Rights Watch report accuses the Indian military and Indian government backed paramilitaries of "committing serious and widespread human rights violations in Kashmir." One such alleged massacre occurred on January 6, 1993 in the town of Sopore. TIME Magazine described the incident as such: "In retaliation for the killing of one soldier, paramilitary forces rampaged through Sopore's market and bookshops, ablaze and shooting bystanders. The Indian government condemned the event 'unfortunate' and claimed that an ammunition dump had been hit by gunfire, setting off fires that killed most of the town." In addition to this, there have been claims of disappearances by the police of the army in Kashmir by several human rights organizations.

Many human rights organizations such as Amnesty International and the Human Rights Watch (HRW) have condemned human rights abuses in Kashmir by Indians, such as "extra judicial executions," "disappearances" and torture that "Armed Forces, Special Powers Act"

which "provides impunity for human rights abuses and fuels cycles of violence. The Armed Forces Special Powers Act (AFSPA) grants the military wide powers of arrest, the right to shoot to kill, and to occupy or destroy property in counterinsurgency operations. Indian officials claim that troops need such powers because the army is only deployed when national security is at serious risk from armed combatants. Such circumstances, they say, call for extraordinary measures." Human rights organizations have also asked Indian government to repeal the Public Safety Act, since "a detainee may be held in administrative detention for a maximum of two years without a court order." One 2008 report determined that Indian Administered Kashmir, was 'partly Free', (where as Pakistan administered Kashmir was determined 'Not Free').

Communal conflicts between religious groups (mostly between Hindus and Muslims) have been prevalent in India since around the time of its independence from British Rule. Among the oldest incidences of communal violence in India was the Moplah rebellion, when Militant Islamists massacred Hindus in Kerala. Communal riots took place during the partition of India between Hindus/Sikhs and Muslims where large numbers of people were killed in large-scale violence.

The 1984 Anti-Sikh Riots was a four-day period during which Sikhs were massacred by members of the secular-centrist Congress Party of India; some estimates state that more than 2,000 were killed. Other incidents include the 198 Hashimpura massacre during communal riots in Meerut, 1992 Bombay Riots and the 2002 Gujarat violence—in the latter, more than 1,000 Muslims (no citation) were killed following a militant Islamist attack on a train full of Hindu pilgrims in the Godhra Train Burning, where 58 Hindus were killed. Lesser incidents plague many towns and villages; representative was the killing of five people in Mau, Uttar Pradesh during Hindu-Muslim rioting, which was triggered by the proposed celebration of a Hindu festival. Other such communal incidents include the 2002 Marad massacre, which was carried out by the militant Islamist group National Development Front, as well as communal riots in Tamil Nadu executed by the Tamil Nadu Muslim Munnnetra

Kazakhstan against Hindus. The Graham Staines and his children murder case and the various instances of killing and torture of minority Christians along with burning of Christian churches in Orissa and in other RSS stronghold states in India only multiply the cases of religious violence in India.

Conflicts such as Anti-Bihari sentiment have sometimes escalated to violence. Invasive methods like 'narcoanalysis' (controlled anaesthesia) is now commonly permitted by Indian courts for crime investigation. Even though according to Indian Constitution "nobody may be made a witness against himself", courts have recently proclaimed that even a permission from court is not necessary for conducting this practice. Narcoanalysis is now widely used to replace/circumvent the lack of skill and infrastructure for conducting scientific methods of crime investigation. Narcoanalysis is also alleged as against medical ethics.

It has been found that more than half of the prisoners of the country are detained without adequate evidence. Unlike in other democratic countries, the investigation in India generally commence with the arrest of the accused. As the judicial system is understaffed and sluggish, it is not uncommon to find innocent civilians languishing in jail for many years. For instance, the Bombay high court in September 2009 asked the Maharashtra government to pay Rs 1 lakh as compensation to a 40-year-old man who languished in prison for over 10 years for a crime he didn't commit.

Mahatma Gandhi's experiences of human rights violation in South Africa changed his life. While he was there, he came face to face with blatant racism and discrimination of a kind that he had never witnessed in India. The humiliation he felt at the hands of officials turned him from a meek and unassertive individual into a determined political activist. He had originally gone to South Africa on a one year contract to work for an Indian law firm in Natal Province. There he took up various grievances on behalf of the Indian community and gradually found himself, first as their advocate on civil rights issues and finally as their leader in a political movement against racial discrimination and for South African Indian

rights. His methods were unusual. He launched a struggle against the authorities which in keeping with his strict Hindu beliefs was based on a strict adherence to non-violence. This meant that it consisted of passive resistance - the peaceful violation of certain laws, the courting of collective arrests (he urged his followers to fill the jails), non-cooperation with the authorities, boycotts and spectacular marches. These methods were later to be perfected back in India in the fight for independence from the British Empire.

Gandhi's ideas were gradually perfected as a result of his South African experiences. Throughout his life, the ideas he formed in these first few years in South Africa were to be developed to fit various changed circumstances in the fight for Indian independence. They were, however, set within a global context of a total rejection of modern civilization. His rejection of 'modern' or Western civilization was all encompassing. He described it as the 'Kingdom of Satan' polluting everyone it touched. Modernization in the form of industrialization, machinery, parliamentary government, the growth of the British Empire and all the things that most people regarded as progress, Gandhi rejected. In opposition to modern civilization, he counter posed ancient Indian civilization with its perceived emphasis on village communities that were self-sufficient and self-governing. He was concerned with the stranglehold that Western civilization had over India. The materialistic values that the British Raj imposed on India had to be countered by the spirituality of Ancient India. Time and time again throughout his life he would return to this theme of the need to revert to what he called their 'own glorious civilization' which was far superior to anything modern society could offer.

The professionalising of the non-governmental sector has had an impact on finding public space for certain issues and in making work on the issues sustainable. Child labour, AIDS-related work, the area of devolution and aiding women's participation in pay-at institutions, and battling violence against women have found support and sustainability in funding infrastructure development and support. These have created adequate civil liberties, groups, and initiatives, practices,

campaigns such as the Campaign for the Right to Information based in Rajasthan, the development struggle which has the Narmada Bachao Andolan at its helm, or the fishworkers' forum that has combated, sometimes successfully, the encroachments by the large-scale and capital-intensive into the livelihoods of traditional fishing communities.

Movements for self-determination, militancy, dissent and the nonviolent movement have provoked various extraordinary measures which have, in turn, prompted human rights groups into protest and challenge. The Terrorist and Disruptive Activities (Prevention) Act (TADA) is an instance. The Armed Forces Special Powers Act (AFSPA) continues. Encounter killings, disappearances and the ineffectiveness of the judicial system in places where 'extraordinary' situations of conflict prevail, characterise the human rights-related scenario. A jurisprudence of human rights has emerged in these contexts.

Networking, and supporting each other through conflicts and campaigns, is not infrequent. There are glimmerings of the emergence of, or existence of a **human rights community** in this. This has had groups and movements working on tourism, forest dwellers rights, civil liberties, displacement, women's rights and environment. For instance, finding a common voice in protesting the nuclear blasts in May 1999, or in condemning the attacks on the filming of 'Water' which had undisguised communal overtones. There has also been a building of bridges across causes and the emergence of an inter-woven community of interests.

As the vista of rights has expanded, conflicts between rights have begun to surface. There has been a consequent prioritisation of rights. The determination of priorities has often depended on the agency which engages in setting them- sometimes this has been environmental groups, at others workers, and yet other times, it has been the court, for instance.

In this general setting, we embarked on a mapping of

- human rights issues
- responses- state and non state- to human rights situations

- conflicts between rights and prioritisation of rights, and
- a miscellany of issues including the treatment, and the place of state and non-state violence, and the question of who speak for whom, and the relationship between the advocate of an interest and the persons or classes of person affected by the advocacy.

In the past decade the context of human rights in India has been influenced by

- the state policy of liberalisation
- the internationalising of human rights
- a prioritising of rights that has occurred particularly through the agency of the court, and even as the human rights and development communities have been working at breaking down the barriers between rights.

Liberalisation, and the concerted moves towards opening up the Indian market and the valorisation of the market economy; and the various initiatives to attract foreign direct investment has resulted in a re-prioritisation of a range of rights, including in the area of project displacement, workers' rights and the casualisation of work, exclusion of local populations from forests and from livelihood access including, for example, in fisheries. The restructured role of the state as a contracting party with multinational corporations and with international financial institutions, has altered the nature of the dialogue between the state and the affected peoples. The study constantly met with concern about disjunction between emerging state policy and the insecurities among people who are either victims of this 'growth' model, or who apprehend that they may be wiped out in the process.

In the early 1990s, there was talk of 'safety nets' and re-training of the workforce rendered redundant in this growth model. In the late 1980s, and early 1990s, a re-negotiation of the equation of cost-benefit was recognised by the state as inevitable, and there was an acknowledgment of the need for introducing land for land when involuntary displacement

occurred.

The displacement contestation, moving from being a stir and an agitation to a challenge to the development model which often excludes those who pay the price, has been one expanding challenge to a notion of development which threatens, and deprives, continuity of life and community. causes impoverishment, and witnesses disappearing livelihoods and exclusion. The Aruvari Sansad experience in Alwar district of Rajasthan has begun to be a model for the regaining of control over local resources, and its possible rejuvenation. The Right to Information Campaign initiated by the MKSS has been adopted widely to vitalise notions of accountability, transparency and to alter the equation between the state and the people.

The internationalising of human rights has had a range of effects. International pressure, both from governments and from organisations such as the Amnesty International, led to the government establishing the NHRC. The link that is made between human rights and trade, and the 'social clause' that has been under discussion, has, on the other hand, resulted in a wariness - both with the state, and among a number of human rights and development activists. This threat of intervention in the arena of human rights with the possibility of sanction has been one overt cause for hostility to international instruments which deal with human rights standards and conduct. The Torture Convention, the Optional Protocol to the Geneva Convention, reservation while ratifying the CEDAW, and the non-consideration of signing the statute for the establishment of the International Criminal Court are premised at least in part on this apprehension. Human rights and development activists have begun to reach international - particularly UN - organisations to represent their cause, and use them to demand accountability from the state. This is true with the report presented to the Human Rights Committee, under the CEDAW, for instance. The preparing of alternative country reports has also been a process of comparing state and non state priorities.

The theme of impunity remains inadequately represented in all of this.